

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$ from Special Relativistic Complementarity of Frames?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 12, 2025

In Newtonian mechanics, a particle with rest mass m_0 at rest is not the same as one that has been accelerated to a speed v and has $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$. A perhaps surprising situation, as is well known in the literature, is that if one has two frames moving at a constant $-v$ to each other, a person in one frame may see a particle at rest, while the person in the other frame sees it as moving and a vice versa scenario. In other words, there exists a complementarity of frames moving at constant speeds to each other (as is well-known) which seems to lead to the equations of special relativity. We suggest that complementarity of frames means that there should exist an equation (equivalence) between m_0 in one frame and m_0 , KE and p (or more generally E, p, m_0) in the other. We have argued in previous notes that because $KE = \frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ and is not dependent on the sign of v , it should be linked with m_0 and d ($d = \text{constant speed}$). One may then write: $(m_0 d + \frac{1}{2}mv^2) / (m_0 d + \frac{1}{2}mv^2) - p^2/d^2 \approx m_0^2/d^2$ which ultimately leads to the special relativistic: $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ ((1)). At this point there is no notion of spin.

Here we argue that if complementarity of frames means that one must have an equation linking m_0 in one frame to m_0 , KE , p in the other (or really E, p in different frames), then there is a second mathematical way of creating such an equation. Furthermore, this equation is consistent with ((1)). In fact, this equation (containing matrices and numbers) is obtained from the Dirac equation (1) by replacing $i \partial/\partial t$ with E and $-i \partial/\partial x$ with p , both numbers. Such an equation, linear in p , E and m_0 and containing matrices, should also represent special relativistic frame complementarity, although the presence of the matrices may suggest that one is dealing with a different kind of particle than one simply satisfying ((1)). The reason we suggest this is that one may use the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ in ((1)) with $E \rightarrow i \partial/\partial t$ and $p \rightarrow -i \partial/\partial x$. E and p are now linked to operators and are on a similar footing to matrices which may also be seen as operators. Matrices act on vectors and so $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ would need to be multiplied by a vector (4-vector) in the linear case, but not in the case of a simple $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ solution of ((1)). This seems to suggest two kinds of particles (called spin 0 and spin $\frac{1}{2}$). The point we try to make is that both arise from the complementarity of frames of special relativity.

Complementarity of Frames in Special Relativity

Special relativity is a theory which goes beyond Newtonian mechanics and seems to be largely based on the notion of complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed with respect to each other. To see this notion, first consider a particle with rest mass m_0 which is accelerated following Newtonian physics. It then has m_0 , $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$. Given that a force has been applied there is no complementarity in the Newtonian view.

As is well-known in the literature, a particle at rest in one frame will be seen to be moving by a frame moving at $-v$ to the first (and a vice versa scenario). In other words, one cannot really be sure whether the particle is moving or the frame. This we argue leads to the concept of:

Complementarity of frames moving at constant v to each other.

We suggest that this is equivalent to the condition:

An equation must exist linking m_0 in one frame and m_0 , KE and p in the other (or more generally E, p and m_0).

We suggest that m_0 and $KE = .5m_0v$ are similar objects because they do not change when $v \rightarrow -v$ whereas p does. We group: $m_0 d + .5m_0v$ ($d = \text{constant with speed units}$) and try to link to p . This seems to suggest a quadratic approach:

$$(m_0 d + .5m_0v) (m_0 d + .5m_0v) - p^2 d \approx m_0 m_0 d^2 \quad ((2))$$

More generally, using a transformation matrix:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v) & v/d & g \\ v/d & g & g \end{vmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

One may show that $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/dd}$ and that:

$$EE = ppdd + m_0 m_0 d^2 \quad \text{with } E = m_0 d / \sqrt{1-vv/dd} \text{ and } p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/dd} \quad ((4))$$

In the $v \ll d$ limit, one obtains the Newtonian results as is well-known. (Here $d = c$, the speed of light in a vacuum.)

At this point, one might stop with ((4)), but we suggest that the complementarity of frames idea leads to a second math solution. In particular, ((4)) is not the only equation linking E, p and m_0 .

A Second Equation Satisfying the Special Relativistic Complementarity of Frames Idea

There exists an equation, other than ((4)), which links E, p, m_0 in two frames (i.e. E, p in one and m_0 in the other). In fact, this equation is the Dirac equation, which contains matrices, with $-i\hbar/dt$ replaced with the number E , $-i\hbar/dx$ replaced with the number p and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ removed. (For full details of the Dirac equation and its matrices, see (1).)

Then one has an equation in numbers and matrices (and their vectors) linking E, p and m_0 and we argue that this satisfies the requirement of special relativistic complementarity of frames moving at constant speed with respect to each other. This equation is linear in E, p and m_0 and if one squares each side, one obtains ((4)). Thus, it is consistent with ((4)), but suggests a more complicated solution. In fact, a simple solution of ((4)) might represent one kind of particle and the more complicated one from the linear Dirac number equation, another.

The Idea of Operators

A matrix is an operator which acts on a vector. One may thus ask: Why should one have E , p , m_0 as numbers and then matrices acting on some unusual vectors. This seems to be inconsistent. We have argued in previous notes that we think that free particle quantum mechanics arises from special relativity. In particular, one has the Lorentz invariant for a particle with rest mass m_0 :

$$-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0 \quad ((5))$$

In ((5)), x and t would be presumed to be center-of-mass co-ordinates. Given that $d=c$ appears in relativistic expressions for E, p (see ((4))), it seems that there are also signals moving at c , a speed which is the same in all frames. We have suggested that even though ((5)) holds for the center-of-mass point, $-E \Delta t + p \Delta x = 0$ should hold for the signals (just as it holds for a free photon). This leads to:

$$\Delta t = \text{constant} / E \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x = \text{constant} / p \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is consistent with a function: $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ ((7))

We argue that ((7)) is interaction dependent. For example:

$$\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1 + p_2) x) \quad ((8))$$

Momenta add in an interaction and the new wavelength is constant / $|p_1 + p_2|$ not a sum of the original wavelengths of p_1 and p_2 . Thus, it is the overall interaction which is key. Given this function ((7)), one may use operators $\partial/\partial t$ and $-\partial/\partial x$ to obtain E and p . Thus, in the matrix case, the matrix is an operator just like $\partial/\partial t$ and $-\partial/\partial x$ and the vector is like $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. If one does not wish to accept the idea of $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ as arising from special relativity, one may take it a priori as the free particle wavefunction.

As a result, one has two solutions:

One may simply use $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ in ((1)) with $E \rightarrow \partial/\partial t$ and $p \rightarrow -\partial/\partial x$. This represents a particle with no associated vector which we call spin 0.

In the second case, one has $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ vector which represents a particle with spin.

Given that p and E are interaction variables, one would expect the vector to be linked with interactions as well and it is for charged particles (i.e it interacts with a magnetic field).

As a result, we argue that it is the special relativistic complementarity of frames moving with constant speed to each other which leads to the spin 0 and spin $1/2$ cases of quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of spin 0 and spin $\frac{1}{2}$ are based on the idea of the special relativistic complementarity of frames moving with constant speed with respect to each other. We argue that this principle is responsible for special relativity and implies that one has an equation linking E, p in one frame with E, p in the other. In fact, we argue that one may obtain an approximate expression for this equivalence (equation) using Newtonian mechanics, i.e. linking $m_0, KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$. This leads to a quadratic equation which ultimately becomes: $EE = ppcc + momoccc$, but shows no spin.

We argue, however, that the complementarity of frames implies that one may use any equation linking E, p, m_0 . We suggest that the equation proposed by Dirac may have $i\hbar/dt$ and $-\hbar/dx$ replaced with the numbers E and p and then one has an equation with E, p, m_0 and matrices (and their vectors). We suggest that this is a perfectly fine equation satisfying the complementarity of frames of special relativity. An issue that arises is the presence of E, p, m_0 as numbers and matrices which act on vectors. The Dirac number equation is linear in E, p, m_0 and if one squares both sides one obtains $EE = ppcc + momoccc$, so one has consistency, but this linear equation seems to be more complicated.

We have argued in previous notes that we think that the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px = \text{constant}$ (not=0 ($m_0 > 0$)) is linked to free particle quantum mechanics. In particular, we argue that special relativity shows that there are signals moving with speed c (the same in all frames) for a particle with $m_0 > 0$. Thus, we argue that there should be a solution: $-E \Delta t + p \Delta x = 0$ for a $m_0 > 0$, just as there is such a solution for a free photon. This result is compatible with the function $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and so EE and pp may be replaced with operators based on $E \rightarrow i\hbar/dt$ partial and $p \rightarrow -\hbar/dx$ partial. (Alternatively, one may take $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ to be the quantum free particle wavefunction a priori.)

In such a case, one may use these operators in $EE = ppcc + momoccc$ and create a differential equation. We call this simple solution $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ spin 0. Alternatively, one may use the Dirac equation with $i\hbar/dt$, $-\hbar/dx$ and the matrices as operators acting on $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and the vector and call this solution one with spin (spin $\frac{1}{2}$ in this case). The Dirac equation is linear in E, p and m_0 which are interaction variables so one anticipates that the vector will also be linked with an interaction (i.e. for a charged particle it interacts with a magnetic field).

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dirac_equation